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THE USE OF AI IN LITERARY TRANSLATION: A CASE STUDY OF «ONE DAY IN THE LIFE OF IVAN DENISOVICH»

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Abstract

*The paper examines the features and main challenges of translating classic literature, analyzes the translation of A.I. Solzhenitsyn's novel «One Day in the Life of Ivan Denisovich» by H. T. Willetts, and demonstrates the advantages and disadvantages of using AI for translating classic works from Russian into English. **The purpose of the paper** is to highlight the problems of literary translation and assess the quality of the AI-generated translation of «One Day in the Life of Ivan Denisovich». **The relevance of the study** lies in the fact that AI is one of humanity's most significant recent innovations, gradually entering the field of translation; however, at present, there is almost no analysis of AI's success in translating Russian literary classics. The first part of the article details the differences between modern and classical literature using descriptive and comparative analysis methods. The second part identifies realia as one of the most complex lexical layers, which was satisfactorily conveyed to the English-speaking audience in H. T. Willetts's translation. A historical method was applied. In the final part, the author presents a diagram illustrating the techniques used by AI in translating thirty realia (lexical units) and accentuates the strengths and weaknesses of AI-generated content through specific examples. Component and contextual analysis methods were employed. The research results can be used for an in-depth study of AI's potential in translating classical literature.*

Keywords: *artificial intelligence, classical literature, non-equivalent lexis, realia, translation technique.*

The second half of the 1980s is considered the boundary between the 20th and 21st centuries, serving as a starting point for contemporary authors and literary works. However, the difference between classical and modern literature is not limited to the year of publication – there are also fundamental distinctions in themes, presented issues, and narrative styles.

Classical literature is focused on universal and fundamental existential questions, exploring the nature of human morality, ethical choices, social conflicts, and historical processes. It emphasizes universal human values, the eternal struggle between good and evil, freedom and oppression, power and the individual. Such works are often based on deep philosophical analysis, covering broad historical and social contexts while highlighting the fate of characters amid global changes.

Modern literature, on the other hand, centers on personal experience, inner struggles, and subjective perceptions of the world. It places significant emphasis on identity exploration, psychological trauma, existential loneliness, and adaptation to rapidly changing conditions. The themes are influenced by current global trends, including technological advancements, urbanization, and social transformations. Great attention is given to individual consciousness and personal values, which are often ambiguous and open to multiple interpretations.

Classical literature interprets social and personal conflicts as manifestations of fundamental laws governing human existence. Modern literature, however, tends to avoid sweeping generalizations, instead focusing on the nuances of human experience, the complexity of emotions, and the relativity of personal truths.

The most significant difference between classical and modern literature lies in the language of narration.

Classical literature is characterized by elaborate syntactic constructions, complex multi-clause sentences, extensive descriptions, and a sophisticated system of epithets and metaphors. Archaic vocabulary is often used, featuring outdated grammatical forms and expressions specific to historical periods. Expressive speech plays a crucial role, incorporating elements of elevated, epic style, rhetorical figures, inversions, and repetitions.

Modern literature, by contrast, gravitates toward conciseness, dynamism, and economy of linguistic means. It commonly features short sentences, colloquial structures, informal language, neologisms, and borrowings from professional jargon and slang. Minimalism, deliberate simplification of narration, and fragmented storytelling are frequent stylistic choices. The structure of modern texts may be nonlinear, with intentional breaks in chronology, shifts in perspective, and the integration of elements from other media (such as social networks and messaging apps).

Realia exist in both classical and modern literature, yet they serve different functions and reflect distinct cultural contexts. In modern literature, realia capture the dynamic changes in society, technological progress, urbanization, and the development of digital culture. They often reference mass culture, the internet, brands, political and economic trends, and real-time shifts in global affairs. Additionally, modern realia can be short-lived (such as terminology related to temporary trends and internet slang), making them less stable in language compared to classical realia. Their translation tends to be more flexible, as contemporary phenomena often have equivalents in other cultures due to the widespread use of global and social media.

In classical works, realia are tied to the historical and social characteristics of the author's time. They reflect traditions, ways of life, moral norms, governance

structures, and economic relations. Classical literature frequently features realia associated with everyday life, social hierarchies, state systems, religion, military affairs, trade, and outdated forms of production and economy. These references often require annotations, as they allude to concepts unfamiliar to modern readers. Consequently, translating them requires significant adaptation, as classical realia are usually entirely unknown to foreign audiences. Translators employ footnotes, annotations, and descriptive translations to convey their meaning.

However, translators often strive to preserve the authenticity of the original text, even if it complicates comprehension. Thus, it can be concluded that realia represent one of the most challenging lexical layers to translate.

Over the years of the existence of translation studies as a science, many definitions have been given to realia. The word "realia" itself comes from the Latin adjective "realis," which means "substantial," and currently, it denotes any aspects of reality that are characteristic of a specific country, society, etc. In translation studies, "realia" is a term and a lexical unit, not the phenomena they denote.

In their works, Revzin I.I. and Rozentzveig V.Yu. (1964) call realia "lacuna," that is, units of the vocabulary of one language that cannot be translated into other languages because they denote situations peculiar to the culture of one nation but not observed in another culture.

Barkhudarov L.S. (1975) defines realia as "words denoting objects, concepts, and situations that do not exist in the practical experience of speakers of another language."

Fedorov A.V. (2013) understands realia as words conveying national-specific features.

Vlakhov S.I. and Florin S.P. (1980) made a significant contribution to the study and understanding of the linguistic essence of realia in translation. According to their definition, realia are "words or phrases denoting objects characteristic of the life of one people and foreign to another." These linguists highlight the connotative meaning, national, cultural, and historical coloring of realia, which cannot be translated without additional explanation.

Based on the definitions of realia, three main issues in their translation can be formulated: 1) the absence of a constant translation correspondence due to

the uniqueness of the phenomenon to a specific language and culture; 2) the need to transfer not only the semantic, or denotative meaning but also the connotative meaning, which may be associated with national traditions, cultural aspects, historical background unknown beyond a particular country or society; 3) due to the frequent need for descriptive translation, the target text can quickly become incommensurable and difficult to understand. Thus, realia are rightfully considered one of the most challenging lexical units for a translator.

If AI proves capable of translating the most complex grammatical categories, it is highly likely that the overall quality of its translation will be satisfactory.

Alexander Solzhenitsyn wrote *One Day in the Life of Ivan Denisovich* in 1959, but it was only published in 1962 in the literary magazine *Novy Mir (New World)* after receiving personal approval from Nikita Khrushchev. The novel became a sensation, as it was the first openly published Soviet work depicting the harsh realities of Stalin's labor camps. Soon after, translations into foreign languages, including English, appeared.

The first official English translation was published in 1963 by British journalist Ralph Parker. Since this version was approved by Soviet authorities, it was subjected to censorship. Certain passages were softened or omitted to avoid damaging the Soviet Union's image. While Parker's translation gained widespread circulation, it was later criticized for its overly smoothed-out style and inaccurate rendering of the labor camp slang.

The most accurate and complete translation is by H. T. Willetts, published in 1970. Unlike Parker, Willetts had access to the uncensored original text and translated it without omissions, preserving Solzhenitsyn's stylistic features and prison camp jargon. His translation is considered the best and most authoritative due to its fidelity to the author's tone—a view confirmed by Solzhenitsyn himself.

There are other translations, but Willetts' version remains the canonical edition for English-speaking readers. This is why it will serve as the benchmark for comparison with AI-generated translations.

In his translation, H. T. Willetts employed the following translation techniques: 1) transcription and transliteration, 2) calque (loan translation), 3) functional analogue (approximate equivalence), 4) descriptive translation.

The table below illustrates examples of realia from «One Day in the Life of Ivan Denisovich» and how they were rendered in H.T. Willetts' translation.

Table 1 – H.T. Willetts's translation of realia in English

Реалия	Перевод	Техника перевода
Колхоз	Kolkhoz	Transcription
Гулаг	Gulag	Transliteration
Кировский поток	Kirov wave	Calque
б/у	Secondhand	Functional analogue
Зяблый	A man who's cold	Descriptive translation

Transliteration means translating letter formation of a word in the source language, e.g. vice-president – вице-президент. *Transcription* is based on representing the sound structure of a word in the source language

by correspondent sounds in the target language, operating at the level of phonemes, e.g. speaker – спикер. Both transliteration and transcription become essential when there is a need to preserve the lexical nuances of

realia and maintain their original forms from the source language.

Calque is a literal translation of a word, phrase or part of a word (half-calque), that allows rendering realia from source language into target language by keeping fully its semantic, e.g. *перепасход* – overspend. When it comes to half-calque, it constitutes a form of partial borrowing and involves the creation of new words or phrases; they are constructed using a combination of original material and elements borrowed from foreign words. This hybrid approach allows for a nuanced conveyance of meaning while incorporating both native and foreign linguistic elements, e.g. *декабрист* – Decembrist.

The selection of a closely corresponding term in the target language for a lexical unit in the source language that lacks an exact equivalent is known as *analogue translation*. This process involves choosing a term in the target language that captures the closest possible meaning and conveys the intended sense of the

original lexical unit, even though an exact match may not exist. For example, "public defender," "attorney," and "counsel" can be translated into Russian using the same word "адвокат".

In case it is impossible to create a correspondence using the methods mentioned above for translating non-equivalent lexis, a *descriptive translation* is used that reveals the meaning of realia through an expanded phrase, e.g. *veep hunting season* – период поиска кандидатуры на пост вице-президента. Often, the use of transcription or calque for translating a non-equivalent word is accompanied by a description of the meaning of that word in a special note or footnote. This allows combining the conciseness inherent in transliteration, transcription and calque with ensuring a complete understanding of the occasional correspondence by the audience.

ChatGPT 3.5 translated various excerpts from A.I. Solzhenitsyn's novel «One Day in the Life of Ivan Denisovich», which in total contained thirty realia.

Table 2 – Realia from excerpts of the novel that were translated by AI

вертухай	спецнаряд	нары	Кировский поток	шестерить
баланда	недотыка	придурок	зяблый	Соцгородок
доходяга	бедолага	запретка	пайка	зэк
шмон	кондея с выводом	филонить	параша	бесконвойный
шакалить	Ну, заваруха!	колхоз	шмонать	брюхо
костыль	навесить полную катушку	гулаг	казенная машина	шарашка

AI, like H.R. Willetts, used the following translation techniques: 1) transcription and transliteration, 2) calque (loan translation), 3) functional analogue (approximate equivalence), 4) descriptive translation. The

percentage of each type of translation is presented in the diagram below.

Diagram 1 – The main methods of rendering realia by AI (thirty lexical units)

Thus, based on the obtained data, it can be concluded that the most common techniques used by AI to translate the realities of A. I. Solzhenitsyn's short story *One Day in the Life of Ivan Denisovich* into English are the selection of a functional equivalent and explanatory translation. These methods account for 43% and 27% of the total number of analyzed cultural-specific terms, respectively.

The author examined some of the excerpts in detail.

«А заключённые, уже одетые во всю свою рвань, перепоясанные всеми верёвочками, обмо-

тавились от подбородка до глаз тряпками от мороза, – лежат на **нарах** поверх одеял в валенках и, глаза закрыв, обмирают.»

«And the prisoners, dressed in all their rags, strapped up with every piece of string they have, their faces wrapped in cloth from chin to eyes against the cold, lie on the **bunks** over their blankets in felt boots, eyes closed, barely clinging to life.»

When translating the lexical item «нары» into English, we observe a semantic distortion: it is rendered as «bunk» (a narrow bed that is attached to a wall, especially in a boat or a train), whereas in this case, the term «plank bed» (a bed without a mattress, consisting of boards resting on low trestles) would have been a

more accurate choice, as it better conveys the realities of prisoners' lives.

From a stylistic perspective, we see that the Russian word «нары» belongs to prison slang, while «bunk» is a commonly used, neutral word in English.

«Цезарь богатый, два раза в месяц посылки, всем сунул, кому надо, - и придурком работает в конторе, помощником нормировщика.»

«Caesar is rich – gets parcels twice a month, bribes everyone who needs it – and plays the fool in the office, working as an assistant norm-setter.»

The lexical item «придурок» and its frequently occurring synonym «придурня» refers to a prison position, typically in administrative or service-related work. AI completely lost the meaning of this cultural reference, immediately interpreting it as an offensive Russian word, thus failing to fulfill the communicative function of translation.

«Кто в зоне остаётся, ещё так шестерят: прочтут на дощечке, кому посылка, встречают его тут, на линейке, сразу и номер сообщают.»

«Those who stay in the zone keep snitching like this: they read the name from the board, see who's getting a parcel, meet him right there at roll call, and immediately pass along the number.»

The prison slang lexeme «шестерить» means to personally serve someone, while «шестерка» refers to a person who follows someone's orders without question. In AI translation into English, this linguistic unit was essentially omitted – its meaning was dissolved into the phrase *keep snitching*, which means «to report information behind someone's back, to gossip.» In this case, the semantic component of «serving someone, being in someone's service», was lost in translation. As a result, AI completely altered the meaning of the sentence. The «Russian-English Dictionary with Explanations» provides several translation options for «шестерить»: dance attendance on smb. («ходить на задних лапках»), kowtow to smb. («раболепствовать»), be at somebody's beck and call («быть у кого-либо на побегушках»). While these equivalents do not fully convey the prison slang nuance, they at least preserve the intended semantic meaning of A. I. Solzhenitsyn's text, unlike AI's misinterpretation.

– Ше-восемьсот пятьдесят четыре! – прочел Татарин с белой латки на спине черного бушлата. – Трое суток кондея с выводом!

"Six-eight-five-four!" – read the Tatar with a white patch on the back of his black greatcoat. – "Three days in the cooler with a transfer!"

The phrase «кондей с выводом» is a stable prison expression in Russian. The lexeme «кондей» in criminal jargon means «карцер», or «solitary confinement». «Карцер с выводом» implies that a prisoner is allowed to leave for work during the day, whereas «без вывода» means serving the entire punishment term in solitary. AI translated this phrase as «cooler with a transfer», which significantly distorts the original meaning.

Upon analyzing AI's translation, it becomes evident that equivalence is not maintained at almost any level – denotative, connotative, pragmatic, or aesthetic.

Conclusion

One of the primary challenges of literary translation is the absence of direct semantic and stylistic equivalents for prison slang in English dictionaries. As a result, AI struggles to fully convey the atmosphere of Soviet-era camp life. The two most frequently used AI strategies – descriptive translation and functional equivalence – often lead to omissions, stylistic neutralization, and loss of associative meaning. Consequently, lexical units lose their stylistic coloring and cease to serve as cultural markers.

A fundamental difference is also observed between AI's "cognitive" processes and human artistic translation. In translating classic literature, precision in meaning transfer is crucial, but so is capturing subtle emotional, cultural, and philosophical nuances – something AI cannot fully replicate. While AI can process vast amounts of information and recognize patterns, it lacks human intuition, internal experience, and deep contextual awareness.

In literary translation, a key aspect is the translator's ability to not only convey meaning but also preserve depth, tone, and atmosphere. A human translator can incorporate naturalness and unpredictability, reflecting the complexity and multidimensional nature of human consciousness. AI, on the other hand, operates within strict logical and algorithmic frameworks, making its "thinking" too rationalized and systematized to grasp the full scope of an author's intended message.

AI's technical reasoning, as a structured and predictable system, tends to simplify and regulate meaning. In scientific and technical texts, this is acceptable, as such fields require precise and unambiguous language. However, literary works rely on words and imagery to create layered meanings, and AI struggles to maintain this delicate balance.

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